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Hungry Catfish—Effect of Prey Availability on Movement Dynamics of a Top Predator

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ABSTRACT

1. The availability and spatial distribution of prey determine the energetic costs of predators foraging and largely drive their space use, activity level and foraging timing. Consequently, predators in ecosystems with different prey availability and distribution should adjust their movement patterns to optimise their foraging success in order to maximise efficiency.
2. The aim of this study was to investigate the ability of a top predator, European catfish (*Silurus glanis*), to adapt its space use, temporal activity and diet patterns in environments with varying prey density and distribution and to examine the consequences for the catfish’s body growth.
3. Catfish activity, tracked with high-resolution acoustic telemetry positioning systems deployed in two oligotrophic lakes with limited fish prey and one eutrophic reservoir with abundant fish prey, showed clear differences in their spatial and foraging behaviour. In oligotrophic, prey-poor lakes, catfish showed larger space use, altered diurnal activity patterns, reduced use of the open water, increased variability in inter- and intra-individual space use and had a more diverse diet compared to their conspecifics in the eutrophic, prey-rich reservoir. The reduced availability of prey in oligotrophic lakes resulted in slower catfish growth, as the adaptations could not fully compensate for the reduced abundance of prey fish.
4. The study showed that top predators can combine different behavioural mechanisms and individual strategies to adapt to different ecological contexts. The observed ability of catfish to adjust activity, space use and diet reflects an adaptive strategy to improve foraging efficiency and overall fitness in varying habitats. These behavioural adaptations may provide catfish with advantages over other top predators in terms of resource exploitation. Such competitive abilities are important for the catfish’s success as an invasive species within Europe.

Milan Říha and Rubén Rabaneda-Bueno contributed equally to this work.

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1 | Introduction

Predator movement and activity dynamics are strongly influenced by species and individual traits, environmental factors and local conditions (Říha and Prchalová 2022), affecting predator growth and trophic interactions (Shaw 2020). Recent advances in in situ animal observation methods offer the opportunity to gain a deeper understanding of individual predator movement patterns, their dynamics and underlying factors (Nathan et al. 2022). This progress has enhanced our ability to observe and analyse predator behaviours across various scales, such as tracking individual movement patterns, assessing key movement drivers and understanding impacts on prey populations and ecosystem dynamics as a whole (Nathan et al. 2022).

Food availability is among the most critical factors determining predator movement patterns, influencing home range size, activity levels and timing (Mitchell and Powell 2004; Zhdanova and Reeb 2006). Numerous studies have demonstrated a negative correlation between predators' home range size or activity and prey density, when predators expand their range or increase activity when prey is scarce (Ferguson et al. 2009; Herfindal et al. 2005; Loveridge et al. 2009). Prey density was also shown to modify species-specific diurnal timing of activity (Orpwood et al. 2006; Hansen and Closs 2005) and the factor is assumed to shape inter-individual differentiation in space use (Campos-Candela et al. 2019).

However, there is a lack of empirical evidence linking food availability to the behaviour of aquatic predators, particularly regarding how multifaceted behavioural patterns can be modified under contrasting contexts of poor and rich food availability. For instance, the correlation between individual home range size or activity and prey density may not be linear (Massei et al. 1997; Scharf 2016; Spiegel et al. 2013) or it can be associated with high inter-individual or temporal variability, reflecting a range of individual responses to prey availability or differences in temporal prey availability (Campos-Candela et al. 2019). Understanding how prey availability influences predator behaviour at different spatial and temporal scales can provide important insights into the adaptive strategies that predators employ, particularly in fluctuating environments where resource scarcity requires behavioural flexibility.

Seasonal changes in movement patterns due to temperature may overshadow the effects of food availability on predator movements. In predatory fish, seasonal variations in temperature play a crucial role in various physiological mechanisms, including locomotor capacity and activity levels (Volkoff and Ronnestad 2020). They can result in reduced activity, especially during the cold season, regardless of food availability conditions. In contrast to this assumption, there are reports suggesting that feeding activity during colder periods may be influenced by body fat reserves (Teletchea et al. 2009). These species may increase their activity during cold periods when their fat reserves are low, but also under conditions of low food availability. However, our knowledge of the behaviour of aquatic predators during the cold season is limited (Říha et al. 2022). For our study on the effects of food availability on predator's movement patterns, we used the European catfish (*Silurus glanis*, hereafter referred to as catfish). As one of Europe's largest freshwater predators, catfish exerts a strong influence on ecosystems and is rapidly spreading as an

invasive species (Encina et al. 2024; Vejřík et al. 2017). The catfish reaches a considerable body size and exerts a strong influence on ecosystems as an apex predator (Vejřík et al. 2017). Previous studies have mainly described a uniform pattern of movement characterised by long periods of residence and prevailing nocturnal activity (Cucherousset et al. 2018). However, recent studies have revealed contextual variations in movement patterns and individual dietary specialisation shaped by the environment (Slavík and Horký 2012; Vejřík et al. 2017, 2023). Laboratory experiments have also demonstrated the ability to change the timing of activity in response to the availability of food (Bolliet et al. 2001). Therefore, it can be expected that food availability in the ecosystem influences the catfish's intensity of movement, the timing of their activity and space use, as well as the resulting individual growth. Despite expectations, there is a lack of empirical studies examining how variations in prey availability influence the movement and activity patterns of catfish in natural settings. Moreover, it remains unclear whether individual differences in behaviour contribute significantly to the observed patterns, particularly under conditions of resource limitation.

Understanding catfish behaviour in varying prey availability contexts is also crucial for effective management strategies, particularly in ecosystems where they have become invasive. This unwanted invasion has caused significant upheaval in various local ecosystems, especially those with lower productivity (De Santis et al. 2024; Encina et al. 2024), making insights into their habitat use, activity timing, diet and individual variation critical for assessing their ecological impact and for effective species management.

The aim of this study is to investigate the ability of catfish as an aquatic top predator to adjust their movements and temporal activity patterns in response to variations in prey density and distribution. Specifically, we aim to determine whether catfish exhibit increased activity levels and expanded spatial use in prey-poor environments, and whether these behavioural adjustments are consistent across individuals and seasons. Our hypotheses are as follows: (i) reduced food availability leads to an increase in activity levels and consequently to expanded spatial use throughout the day during the summer months; (ii) the effects of food availability on spatial use and activity will be less pronounced in the colder months; (iii) reduced food availability will lead to greater temporal and inter-individual variability in spatial use and activity timing, which will persist in both cold and warm months; (iv) increased activity will potentially compensate for lower food availability, leading to similar growth rates in fish prey-poor and fish prey-rich environments. To test these hypotheses, we conducted an extensive tracking study of catfish behaviour over a 6-month period in three man-made waterbodies with different prey availability and its distribution. Two of these lakes were oligotrophic, with limited food resources, while one was a eutrophic reservoir with abundant food resources.

2 | Materials and Methods

2.1 | Study Sites

The study was conducted in three artificial waterbodies with comparable size: two oligotrophic lakes, Milada (50°39' N, 13°58' E; herein referred to as OLIGOT1) and Most (50°32' N,

13°38' E; herein referred to as OLIGOT2) and one eutrophic reservoir, Rimov (48°50'N, 14°29' E; Table 1; herein referred to as EUT), all located in the Czech Republic (Figure 1). OLIGOT1 and OLIGOT2 are recently created post-mining lakes resulting from aquatic restorations of mining pits (aquatic restoration took place from 2001 to 2010 in OLIGOT1 and from 2008 to 2014 in OLIGOT2). The EUT reservoir was built in 1978 by damming the Malse River. Oligotrophic lakes have a similar fish community composition, with roach (*Rutilus rutilus*) and perch (*Perca fluviatilis*) dominating both lakes, while ruffe (*Gymnocephalus cernua*), tench (*Tinca tinca*), European catfish (*Silurus glanis*), northern pike (*Esox lucius*) and pikeperch (*Sander lucioperca*) are less common. In addition, planktivorous maraena whitefish (*Coregnus maraena*) is present in the open water habitat of OLIGOT2 (Říha et al. 2021). In EUT, roach and bream dominate the fish community, while perch and ruffe are less common (Tesfaye et al. 2022). Previous studies indicated that prey availability for catfish is similar in these two oligotrophic lakes, with higher prey availability in littoral and lower prey availability in the open water (Vejřík et al. 2017). On the other hand, in EUT, the littoral and open water prey fish communities are much more numerous (Moraes et al. 2021; Říha et al. 2021). Our population data (Vejřík et al. 2017; Vejřík et al. unpublished data) indicate that catfish density is highest in the eutrophic reservoir, with

densities of OLIGOT1—0.7 ind/ha (6.1 kg/ha), OLIGOT2—1.9 ind/ha (9.7 kg/ha) and EUT—2.1 ind/ha (19.7 kg/ha).

All tracked catfish in oligotrophic lakes were stocked into these lakes for biomanipulation purposes. Stocking occurred from 2011 to 2013 (2–4 years prior to tracking), and catfish from 2012 and 2013 were PIT-tagged prior to stocking. Natural reproduction of catfish was not detected in the lakes before and during the study period. Long-term, regular catfish stocking was conducted in EUT, but catfish also reproduce there naturally (Říha et al. 2009). The stocked catfish were PIT-tagged during stocking after 2012, but the age of the tracked fish could not be determined. Therefore, the origin (natural or stocked) of the tracked catfish could not be distinguished in EUT.

2.2 | Fish Tagging

A total of 45 individuals (15 in each waterbody) were caught by electrofishing (11 individuals), longlining (33 individuals) and angling (1 individual). Individuals were measured, weighed and sexed prior to tagging (Table 2). Acoustic transmitters (Lotek Wireless Inc., Newmarket, Canada), MM-M-11-28-PM,

TABLE 1 | Hydrological parameters of the three study waterbodies.

	Area (ha)	Volume (10 ⁶ m ³)	Max. depth (m)	Mean depth (m)	TP (μg L ⁻¹)	SD (m)	B/P (%)
OLIGOT1	250	36	25	16	5	5	11/89
OLIGOT2	311	70	75	22	2.5	7.7	15/85
EUT	210	34	45	16	26.4	1.7	12/88

Note: TP stands for total phosphorus concentration in water, SD for Secchi depth and B/P for the percentage of water volume in benthic and pelagic habitats.

FIGURE 1 | Locations and bathymetry (blue colour) of the investigated waterbodies and positions of the telemetry systems. The orange colour indicates the position of the Czech Republic where the study was conducted. The dots represent the positions of the individual telemetry receivers.

TABLE 2 | Description of tracked catfish in the three studied waterbodies.

Lake	Total length (cm)			Weight (kg)			Sex
	Max	Mean	Min	Max	Mean	Min	F/M
OLIGOT1	158	117.9	81	23.5	10.7	3.5	4/11
OLIGOT2	114.5	93.3	71	8.4	5	2.1	6/9
EUT	166	116.6	81	35	11.7	3.4	6/9

65×28 mm, mass in air of 13 g, including pressure (all waterbodies), motion (oligotrophic lakes) and temperature (EUT) sensors, burst rate 25 s (oligotrophic lakes) or 15 s (EUT), tag weight between 0.03% and 0.6% of fish body weight, were implanted as described in detail in Řiha et al. (2021, 2022). Fish were caught and tagged between 5 and 10 May 2015 in oligotrophic lakes and between 19 and 20 April 2017 in EUT.

2.3 | Telemetry System

Three separate MAP positioning systems (Lotek Wireless Inc., Newmarket, Canada) were deployed in the three reservoirs to track the tagged fish. Each system comprised an array of Lotek WHS3250 receivers, with 44 receivers deployed in OLIGOT1, 47 in OLIGOT2 and 91 in EUT (Figure 1). A detailed description of the design, deployment and accuracy of the arrays can be found for oligotrophic lakes in Řiha et al. (2021) and for EUT in Řiha et al. (2022). For the purpose of this study, tracking records for the period June–November were selected (year 2015 in oligotrophic lakes, 2017 in EUT).

2.4 | Catfish Growth and Diet Sampling

Catfish populations were monitored over the long term in all three waterbodies as part of the ongoing research efforts (see Vejřík et al. 2017, 2023, 2024 for more details). During these monitoring activities, all captured catfish were tagged using Passive Integrated Transponders (PIT tags; Oregon RFID, Portland, USA) and released back into their respective waterbodies. This tagging included both catfish that were stocked into the waterbodies and those captured during routine sampling. Recaptures of PIT-tagged catfish were used to calculate individual catfish growth. Growth was calculated as the difference between the length at the time of PIT tagging and the last recapture scaled with time (length gain/year). To achieve a sufficient number of recaptures of PIT-tagged catfish for reliable growth assessment, we used data collected between April and November over multiple years: from 2013–2017 in Milada and Most and 2017–2019 in Rimov Reservoir. These growth measurements were conducted over multiple years, and catfish were sampled during the growth period (Table S1). This approach helps balance out seasonal variability, as annual growth measurement includes periods of both fast (growing season) and slow (cold season) growth, thus reducing the impact of short-term fluctuations. If the time interval between capture and recapture was less than 1 year, growth was not calculated.

The stomach contents of the catfish were removed by hand through the open mouth and gullet. The stomach contents were

then identified, measured and weighed or fixed with 70% ethanol for laboratory identification using diagnostic elements such as fish bones (for more details, see Vejřík et al. 2017). This method allows for the precise identification of recently consumed prey, even when only small fragments remain. However, it is common for a substantial proportion of catfish to have empty stomachs, which aligns with the feeding patterns observed in other predatory fish species (Arrington et al. 2002). For more detailed methodology, see Vejřík et al. (2017).

2.5 | Fish Community Sampling

Catfish fish prey availability and distribution were investigated using stratified fish community sampling by gillnet and hydroacoustic surveys. Gillnet sampling covers all available habitats and covers a very wide range of available prey, but they were deployed during twilight and night only. To complement this, we also used hydroacoustic sampling to assess changes in prey density in open water during the day and night to assess diurnal changes in prey availability in pelagic habitats. To compare the availability of fish prey between lakes, we considered all fish species and broad size classes caught (see below), as the catfish is an opportunistic, omnivorous predator that consumes a variety of prey across a wide size range (Copp et al. 2009). Both gillnet and hydroacoustic surveys were conducted in oligotrophic lakes in September 2015 and in EUT in August 2017.

Gillnet surveys were conducted in benthic habitats (two sites in oligotrophic lakes and four sites in EUT) and open water habitats (one site in oligotrophic lakes and four sites in EUT), using 30-m long European standard gillnets with multiple meshes set overnight (more details in Řiha et al. 2021; Tesfaye et al. 2022). At each locality in each waterbody, one series of three survey nets was set in the benthic and pelagic habitats at depths 0–3, 3–6, 6–9 and 9–18 m. In the OLIGOT2 and EUT, a series of three survey nets were also set at depths 18–24, 24–30 and > 30 m. Benthic and pelagic gillnets were 1.5-m and 3-m high, respectively. For this study, only catches of fish older than YOY were considered.

Fish density, expressed as catch per unit effort (NPUE: number of fish caught per 1000 m² of gillnet area per night), was then adjusted by the water volume in both open water and benthic habitats (Table 1). This weighting was applied to account for the differing habitat sizes and to provide a more accurate representation of fish density relative to the available habitat space, ensuring that density estimates reflect differences in habitat volume rather than raw catch numbers alone (Teskaye et al. 2022).

The Simrad EK 60 echosounder (Kongsberg Maritime AS, Horten, Norway) was used for the hydroacoustic evaluation of the fish stocks. Two Simrad ES 120-7C transducers, operating at a frequency of 120 kHz, were set to cover the entire water column simultaneously (horizontally and vertically) during day and night (Draštík et al. 2009; Říha et al. 2021). In the Sonar5-Pro software (CageEye AS, Oslo, Norway), echointegration was used to estimate the density of individual fish while shoals were detected manually. Volume backscattering thresholds were set to -62 dB (40logR), and target strength thresholds were set to -56 dB, corresponding to a fish length of 4 cm. The fish tracks were used as the source for calculating the mean target strength.

2.6 | Data Processing

Locations of individual fish were calculated using proprietary post-processing software UMAP v.1.4.3 (Lotek Wireless Inc., Newmarket, Canada). Filtering and further post-processing of fish locations are described in detail in Říha et al. (2021).

The extent of horizontal area use was calculated using a 95% kernel utilisation distribution (hereafter referred to as KUD). Daytime and nighttime were defined as the time before and after sunset and sunrise, respectively. The exact time of sunset and sunrise on each day was calculated using the R package 'maptools' (Bivand and Lewin-Koh 2015), and UD was calculated using the R package 'adehabitatHR' (Calenge and Fortmann-Roe 2019). Further details of UD calculation are given in Říha et al. (2021). The activity of fish was calculated as horizontal swimming speed (expressed in meters per second) between two consecutive positions.

To test the importance of an open water habitat for catfish in all three waterbodies, the proportion of time spent in open water was calculated (TOW). Each mean position was assigned to be either in the benthic (distance < 5 m from the bottom) or in the open water habitat (≥ 5 m from the bottom), and the ratio between the number of open water and benthic locations was calculated.

2.7 | Statistical Analysis

To investigate catfish space use and activity in the three waterbodies, we created a Generalised Additive Mixed (GAM) model. This model incorporated the daily time series (time) spanning a 6-month period as a smoothing component, with waterbody identity coded as a parametric factor. Additionally, to address residual autocorrelation, we integrated a serial autocorrelation into the model, ensuring independence from immediately adjacent observations. We defined both monthly (*month*, starting in June) and time of the day (*tod*, range 0–24 h) variables to account for seasonality during the study period. Waterbody identity was also included as a by-group variable to fit different temporal trends by each waterbody. Together with catfish body length and sex, both seasonal components, *tod* and *month*, were fitted with thin plate and cubic spline functions, respectively. The suitability of including an interaction between the seasonal components (*tod-by-month*) was tested

with different smoothing and tensor product terms. In separate models using a subset of the data from each waterbody, we accounted for differences in fish trajectories (slopes over time) by including random smooth factors for each fish identity tag (fishID), which allowed us to estimate the temporal change as a function of variability within each waterbody (see [Supporting Information](#) for more details). The models were fitted using the *bam()* function from the R package 'mgcv' (Wood 2021) using a restricted maximum likelihood method, adopting a Gaussian error distribution and identity link function. Model comparisons were conducted via likelihood ratio tests, where minimal variance differences favoured the simplest model. We tested the consistency of the behaviour using the GAM models as in Jarić et al. (2022).

For analysing open water habitat use (TOW), we employed Generalised Additive Models for Location, Scale and Shape (GAMLSS) (Stasinopoulos and Rigby 2007) fitted using the R package 'gamlss' (Rigby and Stasinopoulos 2005) with a one-inflated beta distribution. TOW encompasses values in the interval [0,1], reflecting varying levels of open water habitat use (i.e., TOW_p), where a value of 1 indicates maximal open water utilisation (i.e., TOW_l). Models were fitted separately for each waterbody, comprising three distribution parameters: the mean μ , variance (scale) σl and ν denoting the point probability at 1 (detailed parameterisation of the GAMLSS models is available in the [Supporting Information](#) and Říha et al. 2021). In the TOW model, we incorporated the interaction between time, fitted with a cubic smoothing spline, and diel period to account for temporal variability across waters. Additionally, body length was included with a penalised P-spline to address potential size effects. Model selection was guided by the Schwartz information criterion (SBC) values to select the smooth terms and the composition of each distribution parameter (see [Supporting Information](#) for more details). A random smoothing function accounted for inter-individual variability, and an autocorrelation structure accounted for residual correlation.

We used general linear models to evaluate differences in individual catfish growth (dependent variable: annual length gain) across the different waterbodies. Waterbody identity and fish body length were included as explanatory variables. Predicted growth values for each waterbody, along with pairwise comparisons, were calculated using the emmeans package (Lenth 2024).

3 | Results

3.1 | Daily Horizontal Space Use

Daily horizontal space use (HSU) was highest in OLIGOT1 (mean \pm SE: 22.47 ± 2.59 ha/day, $t = 8.67$, $p < 0.001$), followed by OLIGOT2 (16.97 ± 2.62 ha/day, $t = 6.48$, $p < 0.001$), and the lowest in EUT (14.64 ± 2.61 ha/day, $t = 5.61$, $p < 0.001$; Figure 2a). In OLIGOT1, HSU was higher than in EUT and OLIGOT2 throughout the whole period, with the exception of the latter lake in July, when HSU in OLIGOT2 was comparable to or slightly higher than in OLIGOT1 (Table 3, Figure 2b).

FIGURE 2 | (a) Comparison of the mean catfish daily horizontal space use between the waterbodies. The asterisks indicate the significance of the differences ($*p < 0.05$, $**p < 0.01$, $***p < 0.001$); (b) seasonal and (c–e) diel development of the mean daily horizontal space use estimated by the GAM models; individual trajectories of horizontal space use during the day (f–h) and at night (i–k) estimated by the GAM models. R , adjusted repeatability index calculated from the final fit model. The dashed lines (i–k) show the average individual mean daily horizontal space use.

Overall, the nocturnal HSU in the three waterbodies was higher than the daytime HSU (Table 4). During the night, HSU was highest in OLIGOT1 and lowest in OLIGOT2 ($p < 0.001$; Figure 2c–e). The difference between day and night was particularly pronounced in EUT ($p < 0.001$) and significantly lower in the two oligotrophic lakes (both $p < 0.001$, Table 4). In EUT, catfish used

significantly less horizontal space during the day than in oligotrophic lakes ($p < 0.001$, Table 4, Figure 2c–e). Individual and inter-individual variations were lower in EUT than in the oligotrophic lakes (Table 5; Figure 2f–k). Comparisons between day and night reflected this pattern, with EUT showing the lowest repeatability (Table 5; Figure 2f–k).

TABLE 3 | Differences in the mean activity and spatial use of fish in lakes OLIGOT1, OLIGOT2 and EUT from June to December, modelled by generalised additive mixed (GAM) models.

<i>A. Parametric coefficients</i>	HSU		Mean activity	
	Estimate (SE)	<i>t</i>	Estimate (SE)	<i>t</i>
(Intercept)	22.46 (2.59)	8.67***	0.08 (0.005)	14.298***
OLIGOT2	-5.51 (3.68)	-1.50	-0.01 (0.01)	-0.789
EUT	-7.82 (3.68)	-2.13*	-0.001 (0.01)	-0.123
<i>B. Smooth terms</i>	Edf (Ref. df)	<i>F</i>	Edf (Ref. df)	<i>F</i>
s(Time)×OLIGOT1	1.99 (9.00)	2.03***	6.93 (9.00)	128.40***
s(Time)×OLIGOT2	6.05 (9.00)	11.70***	7.08 (9.00)	66.60***
s(Time)×EUT	1.77 (9.00)	2.00*	7.27 (9.00)	42.65***
s(body length)			1.95 (9.00)	3863***
te(month, tod):OLIGOT1			87.24 (137.00)	10.15***
te(month, tod):OLIGOT2			45.82 (137.00)	3.83***
te(month, tod):EUT			113.60 (137.00)	34.30***
s(fishID)	40.43 (42.00)	33.92***	38.093 (41.00)	36.37***
Adjusted R^2	0.42		0.22	

Note: Separate smoothing trends were applied to each lake, with a group-by term for the time-spline function and controlling for body length effects. A cyclic cubic regression spline with a tensor product function estimated smooth interaction surfaces between time of day (tod) and month. Random smooth intercepts for fish identity (fishID) were included to address individual variability. The adjusted R^2 and the scale parameter (ϕ) were estimated directly from the model, the latter being associated with the residual variance. Signif. codes: * $p < 0.05$; ** $p < 0.01$; *** $p < 0.001$.

3.2 | Activity

Catfish activity changed nonlinearly during the study period, and the overall activity was similar in all waterbodies (Table 3), with a peak from June to August and a subsequent decline (Figure 3a). The average swimming activity was very similar in OLIGOT1 (mean \pm SE: 0.078 ± 0.005 km/h, $t = 14.30$, $p < 0.001$) and EUT (0.077 ± 0.005 km/h, $t = 14.12$, $p < 0.001$) and lowest in OLIGOT2 (0.07 ± 0.006 km/h, $t = 12.30$, $p < 0.001$) without a significant difference (Figure 3a). Diurnal activity varied considerably between waterbodies (Table 4), especially from June to September, mirroring the pattern in HSU (Figure 3b–g). In EUT, catfish were less active during the day (mean \pm SE: 0.06 ± 0.006 km/h, $t = 10.48$, $p < 0.001$) and doubled their activity at night (0.12 ± 0.006 km/h, $t = 21.32$, $p < 0.001$) (Table 4, $p < 0.001$), while no such large differences between day and night were observed in the two oligotrophic lakes (Table 4, Figure 3b–g).

Average activity in the three waterbodies varied to a similar extent between and within individuals, both during the day and at night, with individual variability generally greater than inter-individual differences. Only in OLIGOT1 were the individual differences between day and night significant, being twice as high at night as during the day (Table 5; Figure S1).

3.3 | Habitat Use

In general, catfish used the open water only partially (waterbody (μ); $p(0 > TOW < 1)$) with a proportion roughly comparable between the two oligotrophic lakes ($TOW_p = 0.31$ and 0.34 , respectively) and higher in EUT ($TOW_p = 0.48$; Table 6, Figure S3). The

probability of catfish fully utilising the open water habitat (waterbody(ν); $p(TOW = 1)$) was highest in OLIGOT2 ($TOW_t = 0.10$), followed by EUT ($TOW_t = 0.04$) and OLIGOT1 ($TOW_t = 0.03$). In OLIGOT1, there were no significant overall differences in the TOW_p rates between day and night (diel period (μ), day = 0.32 ; night = 0.36 , $p = 0.15$), although the temporal trends tended to diverge in opposite directions (Table 6; Figure 4). In OLIGOT2, the TOW_p proportion was higher at night than during the day (diel period (μ), day = 0.27 ; night = 0.34 , $p < 0.01$) and temporal patterns did not differ significantly. In EUT, TOW_p was higher at night than during the day (diel period (μ), day = 0.44 ; night = 0.52 , $p < 0.01$), and these differences persisted over the studied period, with a tendency to increase during the day and decrease at night (Table 6; Figure 4, Figure S3).

3.4 | Growth and Diet of Catfish

Individual growth varied significantly between the waterbodies (ANOVA, $p < 0.001$), with EUT showing the highest growth (Figure 5a). In all waterbodies, fish were the main food for the catfish, with the catfish in EUT concentrating almost exclusively on fish. In the oligotrophic lakes, the catfish diet was more diverse and included, to a greater extent, crayfish in OLIGOT1 and birds in OLIGOT2 (Figure 5; Table S2).

3.5 | Fish Prey Availability and Distribution

In EUT, the fish gillnet NPUE was considerably higher compared to oligotrophic lakes (Figure 6). The main difference was observed in open water habitats, with 52–88 times higher NPUE

TABLE 4 | Model differences in HSU and mean activity between day and night.

A. Parametric coefficients	HSU						Mean activity					
	Day			Night			Day			Night		
	Estimate (SE)	t	F	Estimate (SE)	t	F	Estimate (SE)	t	F	Estimate (SE)	t	
(Intercept)	13.49 (1.55)	8.70***		16.10 (1.91)	8.44***		0.08 (0.01)	11.67***		0.10 (0.01)	11.83***	
OLIGOT2	-4.11 (2.21)	-1.86		-4.14 (2.70)	-1.53		-0.01 (0.01)	-0.57		-0.01 (0.01)	-0.89	
EUT	-7.31 (2.21)	-3.32***		-2.85 (2.71)	-1.05		-0.01 (0.01)	-1.56		0.01 (0.01)	0.98	
B. Smooth terms	Edf (Ref. df)	F	Edf (Ref. df)	F	Edf (Ref. df)	F	Edf (Ref. df)	F	Edf (Ref. df)	F	F	
s(Time)×OLIGOT1	3.26 (9.00)	10.90***	0.001 (9.00)	0.00	6.23 (9.00)	27.17***	4.05 (9.00)	32.99***				
s(Time)×OLIGOT2	6.51 (9.00)	15.96***	3.23 (9.00)	2.80***	5.80 (9.00)	17.94***	4.48 (9.00)	19.92***				
s(Time)×EUT	0.40 (9.00)	0.062	1.37 (9.00)	3.65***	6.75 (9.00)	7.44***	1.00 (9.00)	59.55***				
s(bl)					1.63 (9.00)	157.69**	1.66 (9.00)	221.38**				
s(fishID)	39.75 (43.00)	22.95***	40.66 (43.00)	34.98***	36.22 (41.00)	11.43***	36.88 (42.00)	13.70***				
Adjusted R ²	0.37		0.39		0.27		0.42					

Note: Models were fitted separately for day and night datasets using separate smoothing trends for each lake and accounting for the effects of body length. Random smooth intercepts for fish identity (fishID) were included to account for individual variability. Signif. codes: * $p < 0.05$; ** $p < 0.01$; *** $p < 0.001$.

in EUT. Hydroacoustic estimates yielded similar results, with higher open water fish density in the reservoir in both diel periods (Figure 6). OLIGOT2 had a slightly higher gillnet and hydroacoustic abundance of fish than OLIGOT1 in both habitats and diel periods (Figure 6).

4 | Discussion

Our study suggests that catfish exhibit different spatial movement behaviour in oligotrophic lakes with low fish prey abundance than in a eutrophic reservoir rich in fish prey. According to our predictions, the HSU and diurnal activity patterns differed between waterbodies. In oligotrophic lakes, catfish increased their diurnal activity and space use and decreased their nocturnal activity (hypothesis 1). The differences in the distribution of fish prey between waterbodies also likely led to a differentiation in catfish habitat utilisation, with the open water zone in EUT being used more intensively. These behavioural differences decreased in the colder months (hypothesis 2). The variability of space utilisation among and within individuals was higher in the oligotrophic lakes than in EUT, but seasonal development of these activity parameters was similar in all waterbodies (hypothesis 3). The change in diurnal behaviour in the oligotrophic lakes did not fully compensate for the lower food availability, resulting in lower catfish growth in these lakes (hypothesis 4). In addition, catfish prey was more diverse in the lakes with lower food availability.

4.1 | Space Use and Activity

Space use and activity differed mainly during the day in summer between poor and rich fish prey systems when catfish in oligotrophic lakes showed comparable activity to that at night and used a similar horizontal space. In EUT, on the other hand, the catfish were mostly inactive during the day and significantly increased their space utilisation and activity at night.

The observed differences in space use and activity patterns among waterbodies could represent an adaptive strategy to optimise resource use in response to differences in prey availability. Catfish are nocturnal species (Boujard 1995; Pohlmann et al. 2001) but are able to adapt their activity to the time of higher prey availability, as documented in laboratory conditions (Bolliet et al. 2001; Boujard 1995). Prey abundance showed large differences in our study, with the density of fish prey in the eutrophic reservoir being between 8 and 25 times higher (in terms of gillnet abundance) than in the two oligotrophic lakes. Alteration of catfish diurnal activity patterns in oligotrophic lakes is therefore most likely due to the overall lower prey abundance, which was insufficient to satisfy the catfish's energy requirements and forced the catfish to forage during the day as well.

4.2 | Seasonal Development of Activity and Space Use

Our results showed similar seasonal development of space use and activity across all studied waterbodies. Previous research has indicated that catfish activity peaks within a temperature

TABLE 5 | Repeatability of the mean activity and daily horizontal space utilisation of fish by lake and time of day.

Lake	Diel period	Mean activity			HSU		
		R	VfishID	Ve	R	VfishID	Ve
OLIGOT1	Day	0.20	0.0006 [0.0003–0.0014]	0.0025 [0.0024–0.0026]	0.39	70.61 [33.20–150.16]	109.36 [103.18–115.90]
	Night	0.28	0.0012 [0.0005–0.003]	0.0030 [0.0028–0.0031]	0.52	106.06 [50.19–224.14]	97.92 [92.51–103.65]
OLIGOT2	Day	0.12	0.0003 [0.0001–0.0007]	0.0022 [0.0021–0.0023]	0.31	26.55 [12.23–57.63]	58.73 [54.77–62.99]
	Night	0.23	0.0007 [0.0003–0.002]	0.00225 [0.0021–0.0024]	0.27	21.78 [10.09–47.03]	57.54 [54.09–61.21]
EUT	Day	0.17	0.0005 [0.0002–0.001]	0.0026 [0.0024–0.0027]	0.22	9.41 [4.08–21.75]	33.45 [31.20–35.87]
	Night	0.21	0.00065 [0.0003–0.0015]	0.0024 [0.0022–0.0025]	0.33	32.59 [14.93–71.16]	66.31 [62.18–70.71]

Note: Data show only the adjusted (R_{slope}) R -values calculated from the final fit model, with 95% confidence intervals calculated using GAMs of increasing complexity, starting with random intercepts and including fixed effects and random slopes. The variance components are also shown for the selected model. The variances of the random effects for each covariate are calculated by dividing the estimated scale parameter (ϕ) by the smoothing parameter (λ) of the fitted model. Repeatability was calculated using a nonlinear approximation following Nakagawa and Schielzeth (2010) as the ratio between the inter-individual variance and the total phenotypic variance such that $R = V_{fishID} / (V_{fishID} + V_e)$, where V_{fishID} is given by the random smooth intercept $s(fishID)$ and V_e corresponds to ϕ and represents the intra-individual variability associated with the random effects (see Supporting Information for more details on the calculations of the variance and R indices).

FIGURE 3 | (a) Mean catfish swimming activity during the tracking period in the waterbodies studied; (b–g) effect of time of day on the swimming activity in each month and waterbody, with the mean time of sunset and sunrise (dashed lines) and the time of daylight in yellow.

TABLE 6 | GAMLSS analysis of the pelagic habitat use in three lakes as a function of the proportion of time spent in open water (TOW).

Parameter	Variable	OLIGOT1		OLIGOT2		EUT	
		<i>b</i> (SE)	<i>t</i>	<i>b</i> (SE)	<i>t</i>	<i>b</i> (SE)	<i>t</i>
μ (logit)	(Intercept)	-1.37*** (0.06)	-24.57	-1.59*** (0.06)	-26.31	-1.10*** (0.06)	-18.78
	cs(time)	-0.00*** (0.00)	-3.65	-0.00*** (0.00)	-11.75	0.00*** (0.00)	18.48
	Diel period [night]	-0.11 (0.07)	-1.44	0.39*** (0.05)	8.42	1.24*** (0.07)	16.92
	pb(body length)	0.61*** (0.02)	28.14	-0.78*** (0.04) ^a	-18.93	-0.13*** (0.02)	-7.84
	cs(time)× diel period [night]	0.00*** (0.00)	5.00			-0.00*** (0.00)	-14.38
σ (logit)	(Intercept)	0.21*** (0.02)	11.92	0.18*** (0.05)	3.57	0.19*** (0.05)	3.91
	cs(time)			-0.00*** (0.00)	-7.14	0.00*** (0.00)	5.95
	Diel period [night]			0.13** (0.04)	3.28	-0.25*** (0.07)	-3.81
	Body length	0.10*** (0.02)	5.85	-0.18*** (0.03)	-5.27	0.07*** (0.01)	4.71
	cs(time)× diel period [night]	-4.10*** (0.15)	-27.05			-0.00** (0.00)	-3.05
ν (log)	(Intercept)	0.10*** (0.02)	5.85	-3.19*** (0.12)	-25.61	-4.10*** (0.24)	-16.86
	cs(time)					0.00*** (0.00)	4.28
	Diel period [night]	0.90*** (0.18)	4.95	0.86*** (0.15)	5.70	-2.43*** (0.31)	-7.87
	SBC	-4350.571		-483.1179		-1014.127	
	GDEV	-4191.402		-1040.216		-1576.828	
	Pseudo- <i>R</i> ²	0.44		0.51		0.44	

Note: In all cases, a one-inflated beta regression was fitted to the data. Fish body length was either included as a linear predictor or fitted with a penalised P-spline using the function pb(), and time was fitted with a cubic spline function cs(). An additive term with random effects and autocorrelation was also included. Signif. codes: * $p < 0.05$; ** $p < 0.01$; *** $p < 0.001$.

Abbreviations: *b*, Variable estimate (z-score); GDEV, global deviance; pseudo-*R*², generalised pseudo-*R*-squared; SBC, Schwartz Bayesian Criterion; SE, standard error; *t*, *t*-statistic.

^aThe predictor was fitted linearly instead of using a smooth function.

range of 25°C–27°C, sharply declining below 10°C (Britton et al. 2007; Copp et al. 2009). Our data corroborate these findings, showing that activity and space use peak in summer and subsequently level off by November in all waterbodies, with activity decreasing to 60%–80% compared to summer, while the decrease in space use was comparatively lower. Oligotrophic lakes showed a greater reduction in space use during the day, while OLIGOT2 and EUT showed a minimal reduction or, in the case of OLIGOT1, no reduction during the night. These results indicate different movement patterns, with both activity and space use decreasing in the oligotrophic lakes during the day, while night activity was less intense but covered a similar area in all waterbodies. While such patterns suggest territorial behaviour during the night, which is consistent with the notion that catfish are territorial (Carol et al. 2007; Daněk et al. 2016), our results showed dynamic seasonal spatial preferences. These preferences were reflected in changes in the open water and depth uses, which did not suggest that they maintained the same territory in the long term. In addition, the marked reduction in diurnal activity and space use in oligotrophic lakes in cooler months could indicate less profitable foraging opportunities during the day or the absence of certain prey such as migratory birds, amphibians or small mammals. In order to gain a more comprehensive understanding of the seasonal development of catfish behaviour, further detailed studies are needed to investigate movement patterns, habitat use and foraging behaviour.

4.3 | Use of Habitat

The occurrence of catfish in the open water habitat was influenced by both the time of day and the characteristics of the waterbody. In oligotrophic lakes, the open water was less important for catfish in general, as they preferred shallow benthic habitats both during the day and at night. These preferences are strongly consistent with the distribution patterns of the prey fish. In oligotrophic lakes, the density of prey fish in the open water was conspicuously low during the day, while the density of open water fish increased at night. Despite this nocturnal shift, the gillnet results indicated that fish densities remained higher in the benthic habitats, and the probability of catfish using the open water increased only slightly. In the eutrophic reservoir, catfish showed a preference for benthic, shallow habitats during the summer days. This preference was probably less influenced by prey distribution, as catfish were less active during the day, and numerous studies have found that catfish rest near underwater structures during the day (Copp et al. 2009). During the night, however, the probability of using the open water increased significantly, with similar utilisation rates observed as in the benthic habitats. While the overall density of prey fish was much higher in the open water, the predominant species in the stomachs of catfish, such as roach, perch and bream, had similar densities in both habitats or were even more abundant in the benthic habitats (perch; our results, also Muška et al. 2018; Říha et al. 2015).

FIGURE 4 | Utilisation of depth by catfish in relation to the bottom depth in each waterbody and at 2-month intervals (polygons representing a 50% core utilisation distribution). The dashed line shows the threshold of 5 m used for the calculation of open water utilisation (TOW parameter).

FIGURE 5 | (a) Individual body growth defined as increment of body length (cm) per year; yellow boxes show the growth of fish used for the telemetry study, and grey boxes show individuals caught during catfish surveys in 2013–2017 in oligotrophic lakes and 2016–2019 in EUT. The numbers in the boxes indicate the number of individuals recaptured (* $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$); (b) composition of catfish prey from stomach content analysis. The first line in the upper part of the picture shows the number of catfish examined with prey in their stomachs, in parentheses the total number of catfish examined for the diet and the second line the number of prey found.

FIGURE 6 | Prey fish abundance in different habitats and times of day: (a) weighted (by volume) gillnet NPUE of prey fish in the open water and benthic habitats; (b) NPUE estimate for the whole water body; and (c) estimate of the mean hydroacoustic fish density in the waterbody in both times of day.

Interestingly, our study showed that catfish were more likely to exclusively use the open water in OLIGOT2 compared to other waterbodies. The exclusive use of open water was individually dependent (see Figure S3), as only a few individuals had a higher probability of using this habitat. These results are consistent with the general trend towards diversification of foraging under limited resources (Campos-Candela et al. 2019) and highlight greater inter-individual behavioural differences in oligotrophic lakes (see below). Overall, these results emphasise the contextual dependence of prey distribution on predator forage behaviour and support previous research indicating the ability of predators to dynamically change their habitats according to prey availability (Brodersen et al. 2015; Cruz-Font et al. 2019).

4.4 | Inter- and Intra-Individual Variability

Although our results suggest that oligotrophic lakes exhibited higher individual variability in space use in comparison to the eutrophic reservoir, OLIGOT1 showed greater individual diversification until early November, while in OLIGOT2 this was mainly the case during the summer. In both lakes and during both periods of the day, individuals divided their space utilisation strategies into mobile and sedentary patterns and maintained them consistently. In the eutrophic reservoir, the space use of individuals depended on the time of day. Individuals pursued a very consistent strategy of low space utilisation and movement during the day and used the space differently at night by adopting a sedentary or mobile foraging strategy to a similar extent as in oligotrophic lakes.

Theoretical studies suggest that in a prey-poor environment, metabolically fast, mobile animals need to increase their space use to meet higher energy requirements compared to slow, resident animals (Campos-Candela et al. 2019), as such inter-individual differences become more apparent. Our results are largely consistent

with this assumption. However, if only food availability was responsible for the variability of individual space use, we would expect similar variability in space use in the two oligotrophic lakes. The study of Vejřík et al. (2023) has shown that oligotrophic lakes exhibit a high degree of individual diet specialisation, in contrast to the situation in the eutrophic lake. An important part of the catfish diet was birds in OLIGOT2 and crayfish and birds in OLIGOT1. The feeding strategies and habitat should differ greatly for the individuals that specialise in this prey, and this suggests that other mechanisms, such as prey type or distribution, may contribute to the individual differences in these lakes.

4.5 | Diet of Catfish and Food Availability

Diet analysis revealed a clear difference in the feeding habits of catfish between the reservoir and the oligotrophic lakes. In the reservoir, catfish favoured almost exclusively fish-type prey, whereas in the oligotrophic lakes they had a broader diet including largely birds (OLIGOT2) or crayfish and birds (OLIGOT1). Although catfish are primarily piscivores (Copp et al. 2009), numerous studies have highlighted their ability to adapt to different food sources and exhibit generalist feeding behaviour (Cucherousset et al. 2018). This foraging flexibility means that catfish in oligotrophic lakes likely forage throughout the day and adapt their foraging habits to take advantage of dynamic changes in food supply. In contrast, catfish in the eutrophic reservoir appear to conserve energy during the day and actively hunt for prey, especially forage fish, at night.

4.6 | Growth

Our results showed that the diet and behavioural flexibility of catfish in oligotrophic lakes did not fully compensate for reduced

food availability, leading to reduced catfish growth. There are several possible explanations for this pattern, with several factors possibly interacting to reduce growth rates. The lower prey density observed in oligotrophic lakes could reduce the encounter rate of catfish with their prey and thus their hunting success, which could otherwise lead to increased foraging activity. In addition, daytime hunting could be less effective overall. Catfish are primarily nocturnal feeders relying heavily on senses other than sight, such as lateral line detection and prey wave detection, as their vision is limited (Pohlmann et al. 2001). Consequently, fish prey in oligotrophic lakes with high transparency may exhibit increased avoidance behaviour, which further impairs the hunting success of catfish. Furthermore, changes in diel activity patterns can mean additional energy expenditure for catfish. Slavík and Horký (2012) documented that catfish with increased daytime activity expended relatively more energy than catfish that adhered to a more typical diel activity pattern.

4.7 | Caveats

We suggest that the significant differences in fish prey abundance are the most plausible explanation for the observed differences in catfish behaviour and growth in the different waterbodies we studied. However, it is important to point out that our study was an uncontrolled experiment conducted without replication in the prey-rich reservoir environment. Therefore, we were not able to establish a direct causal relationship between food availability and the observed behavioural differences between catfish. In addition, our study sites differed in various environmental parameters such as structural complexity, water transparency, maximum depth, prey species composition and oxygen availability. These differences could influence catfish behaviour in ways other than just prey availability. Furthermore, catfish were released into all waterbodies, and previous research has shown increased space utilisation by catfish introduced to the new environment (Monk et al. 2020). However, the study by Monk et al. (2020) indicates a persistent increased activity for months after stocking, while the catfish in our study had already been living in the waterbodies for at least 2 years after stocking and thus had sufficient time to adapt to the new environment.

4.8 | Catfish Impact and Population Management

The results underline the remarkable behavioural and feeding flexibility of catfish, which enables them to cope effectively with different environmental conditions and adapt quickly to local conditions. This flexibility encompasses not only the interactions between diet and feeding behaviour but also the plasticity of individual behavioural traits. This adaptability also probably contributes to the rapid spread of catfish populations in new areas, which have a significant impact on the invaded ecosystems (Vagnon et al. 2022; Vejřík et al. 2019).

Our results also suggest significant effects on the risk for prey to be preyed upon by catfish, which depend on the environmental context. The spatio-temporal differences in catfish activity and habitat utilisation between the oligotrophic lakes and the eutrophic reservoir led to different landscapes of fear within the ecosystems. These differences can have profound effects

on both direct and indirect predator–prey dynamics (Gallagher et al. 2017), potentially impacting not only prey populations but also other trophic levels (Laskowski et al. 2022; Lichtenstein et al. 2023). To date, there is a lack of studies investigating the effects of the environmentally dependent behaviour of apex predators on ecosystems. Therefore, further research is needed to better understand the nuanced interplay between predator behaviour and ecosystem dynamics, especially in the context of changing environmental conditions. This knowledge is crucial for the development of more comprehensive management and conservation strategies aimed at maintaining ecosystem integrity and biodiversity in the face of ongoing environmental change.

Understanding contextual differences in predator foraging and movement patterns can also inform specific management strategies to either enhance or reduce catfish populations. In ecosystems where catfish are invasive and negatively impact native species, targeted removal efforts (such as active fishing with longlines; Vejřík et al. 2024) can be concentrated in areas where catfish exhibit higher foraging activity. In oligotrophic lakes, the primary fishing effort should focus on nearshore benthic areas and can be conducted throughout the day. In eutrophic reservoirs, nocturnal fishing is recommended in both benthic and pelagic areas due to catfish activity patterns. Conversely, in regions where catfish populations need to be maintained or enhanced for conservation or fisheries purposes, management strategies could prioritise habitat improvements, such as increasing prey availability to support catfish forage, or limiting catfish fishing to daytime hours.

5 | Conclusion

Our study highlights the remarkable behavioural flexibility of catfish in coping with different environmental conditions, particularly in response to differences in prey abundance and habitat characteristics between oligotrophic lakes and eutrophic reservoirs. Optimising catfish activity strategies involves a dynamic interplay between evolutionary adaptations and behavioural flexibility that likely enhances the species' ability to thrive in different ecological contexts. By understanding how catfish adapt to different environments, conservationists can better adapt management strategies to maintain and enhance or reduce catfish populations in different aquatic habitats. In addition, further analysis of the long-term consequences of these activity patterns, particularly in terms of growth rates and overall fitness, promises to provide deeper insights into the ecological dynamics of catfish populations in different waterbodies.

Author Contributions

Milan Říha and Rubén Rabaneda-Bueno conceived the ideas and designed methodology; Milan Říha, Lukáš Vejřík, Marek Šmejkal, Martin Čech, Vladislav Draštík, Petr Blabolil, Michaela Holubová, Tomáš Jůza, Karl Ø. Gjelland, Zuzana Sajdlová, Luboš Kočvara, Michal Tušer and Jiří Peterka collected the data; Rubén Rabaneda-Bueno, Milan Říha, Lukáš Vejřík and Vladislav Draštík analysed the data; Milan Říha and Rubén Rabaneda-Bueno led the writing of the manuscript. All authors contributed critically to the drafts and gave final approval for publication.

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Ethics Statement

This study was approved by the Animal Welfare Committee of the Biology Centre CAS (45/2014) according to § 16a of the Act No. 246/1992 Coll., on the protection of animals against cruelty, and Experimental Animal Welfare Commission under the Ministry of Agriculture of the Czech Republic and with permission (Ref. no. 310/7387) of the managers of the study sites, Povodí Vltavy s.p. and DIAMO s.p.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Data Availability Statement

Data available from the github repository <https://github.com/rubenrabb01/Hungry-Catfish-Effects-of-Prey-Availability-on-Movement-Dynamics-of-a-Top-Predator.git>.

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Supporting Information

Additional supporting information can be found online in the Supporting Information section.